

Strengthening School-Based Garden Program: Opportunities and Challenges of Coordinators

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Abstract. This study explored the opportunities and challenges of school coordinators in strengthening the School-Based Garden Program. There were ten (10) teachers of Sta. Cruz North District, Division of Davao Del Sur, who participated in the study. This study used a phenomenological approach to extract the participants' ideas. An in-depth interview was conducted to gather information about their experiences and coping mechanisms. Using the thematic analysis, the following themes emerged: the opportunities and challenges of school coordinators focused on environmental education, life skills development, and community partnership. The identified coping mechanisms with the challenges delved into positive responses, professional development, and innovative concepts. The insights drawn from the study's findings were challenges in sustainability, opportunities for experiential learning, and curriculum integration. Results revealed that school-based garden programs should be strengthened to enhance their impact on student learning and the community. Moreover, stakeholders shall collaborate to promote success and sustainability.

KEY WORDS

1. Life skills 2. community partnership 3. professional development

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1. Introduction

Strengthening a school by implementing a garden program offers a unique and promising approach to education. Integrating gardens into the educational landscape can provide numerous opportunities for students and the school community. However, like any initiative, this endeavor has its set of challenges. Potential opportunities and challenges that coordinators face in their efforts to enhance schools through garden programs are evident. A school garden offers a hands-on, experiential learning environment where students can actively engage with the natural world, promoting a deeper understanding of various subjects like biology, environmental science, and nutrition. Gardens provide a platform to educate students about healthy eating habits, the nutritional value of different foods, and the importance of a balanced diet. This can contribute to improved overall health and well-being. The garden program can cultivate a sense of environmental stewardship among students, teaching them about sustainability, conservation, and the importance of preserving the environment. Working in a garden encourages teamwork, collaboration, and communication, helping students develop essential social and interpersonal skills valuable in academic and personal contexts. School gardens can be a focal

point for engaging the local community, involving parents, volunteers, and organizations. This inclusive approach fosters a sense of community, support, and shared responsibility for the school's success, making everyone feel part of a larger mission. While the benefits of a school garden program are significant, it's important to acknowledge the challenges that come with it. Limited financial resources, access to suitable land, and availability of necessary gardening tools and materials can pose significant challenges to establishing and maintaining a school garden program. Adverse weather conditions, seasonal changes, and extreme climates can impact the growth and maintenance of the garden, requiring careful planning and adaptation of gardening practices. Coordinators need to align the garden program with the curriculum, ensuring that it complements the academic goals and standards of the school. This requires thoughtful planning and collaboration with educators. Ensuring the sustainability of the garden program beyond the initial implementation phase is vital. Coordinators must address issues related to maintenance, volunteer support, and long-term funding. Striking a balance between the educational goals of the garden program and the existing academic curriculum can be challenging. Coordinators must integrate garden-related activities without compromising traditional classroom learning. According to Blair (2009), Australia experiences diverse climates and extreme weather events. Coordinators must adapt gardening activities to suit local climates, considering droughts, heatwaves, and other environmental challenges. Funding, land availability, and access to suitable gardening materials can be limiting factors. Coordinators face the challenge of securing adequate resources to sustainably establish and maintain the garden. Integrating garden activities effectively into the curriculum while meeting educational standards is challenging. Coordinators need to strike a balance between experiential learning and tradi-

tional classroom teaching. Incorporating indigenous plant knowledge and cultural practices in the garden program can be challenging but is essential for promoting respect and understanding of Australia's rich indigenous heritage. Ensuring the long-term sustainability of the garden program is vital. Coordinators must develop strategies for ongoing maintenance, including securing funding, garnering support, and involving students and the community. It is crucial to address disparities in educational access and opportunities across different regions of Australia. Coordinators must ensure that garden programs are accessible and beneficial for students from diverse socio-economic backgrounds. Strengthening schools through garden programs in the Philippines offers unique opportunities and challenges. The country's rich agricultural heritage and natural biodiversity make it an ideal setting for integrating garden programs into the educational system. The Philippines has a strong agricultural tradition. Coordinators can capitalize on this by integrating agricultural education, environmental studies, and sustainability practices through school gardens. School gardens can address food security issues by promoting sustainable farming practices and educating students about diverse crops and nutrition. This aligns with efforts to combat malnutrition and improve overall dietary habits. Gardening and agriculture are deeply ingrained in Philippine culture. Coordinators can utilize the school garden to preserve and celebrate traditional farming practices and indigenous knowledge, fostering cultural pride and understanding. School gardens can serve as community hubs, involving parents, local farmers, and other stakeholders. This collaboration strengthens community ties and encourages collective responsibility for the garden's success. Access to funding, suitable land, and gardening materials can be challenging. Coordinators must find innovative solutions to secure resources and sustain the program effectively. The Philippines is prone to typhoons

and heavy rainfall, affecting gardening activities. Coordinators must adapt gardening practices to the local climate and implement strategies to mitigate weather-related challenges. Aligning the garden program with the curriculum and providing adequate training to teachers for effective integration requires careful planning. Coordinators need to ensure that garden-related activities enhance the learning experience. Sustaining the garden program beyond the initial implementation is crucial. Coordinators must develop strategies for ongoing maintenance, securing funding, and engaging the community to ensure the garden's long-term success. In urban areas, schools may have limited space for gardens. Coordinators must find creative ways to implement garden programs, such as vertical gardening or utilizing community spaces. Coordinators need to ensure that the benefits of the garden program are accessible to students across urban and rural areas, addressing educational disparities and promoting inclusive participation. The "School Inside a Garden" program of Davao Del Sur aims to create a learning environment that incorporates natural surroundings and promotes ecological awareness. This innovative approach integrates education with sustainable practices and environmental appreciation. Students can engage with nature, learn about local ecosystems, and develop a deeper connection with the environment. The program focuses on holistic education, emphasizing academic knowledge and practical skills related to gardening, biodiversity, and conservation. By immersing students in a garden-based educational experience, the program encourages a sense of responsibility toward the environment and fosters a sustainable mindset. Given the agricultural richness of the region, coordinators can emphasize nutrition education and food security by teaching students about diverse crops, balanced diets, and the importance of locally sourced, fresh produce. Davao Del Sur's rich biodiversity offers a unique opportunity to educate students about

preserving and protecting the environment. Coordinators can highlight native plants, conservation efforts, and sustainable environmental practices. Coordinators can encourage collaboration with local farmers, agricultural experts, and environmental organizations to enrich the school garden program. This fosters a sense of community involvement and shared responsibility for the garden's success. Urbanization in Sta. Cruz North District may limit the availability of space for school gardens. Coordinators must carefully plan and utilize the available space efficiently, considering vertical gardening or rooftop gardens. The district's climate and weather conditions may pose challenges for successful gardening. Coordinators must consider weather patterns and adapt gardening practices to suit the local climate. Acquiring resources such as seeds, gardening tools, and funding for infrastructure may be challenging. Coordinators must actively seek support from local government, NGOs, or private donors to secure the necessary resources. Coordinators must invest in teacher training to ensure the effective integration of garden activities into the curriculum. Aligning the garden program with educational objectives and standards was essential for successful implementation. Sustaining the garden program beyond the initial phase is crucial. Coordinators must develop maintenance strategies involving students, teachers, and the community to ensure the garden's long-term growth and impact. Coordinators in Sta. Cruz North District faces limited space, climate sensitivity, resource scarcity, curriculum integration, and sustainability challenges. However, the opportunities tied to agricultural education, nutrition, environmental awareness, and community engagement make school garden programs a promising approach for enhancing education and promoting a sustainable and healthy future in the district. Through this research, we aim to make a positive impact. Coordinating a school garden program presents exciting

opportunities for enhancing education through experiential learning, health promotion, environmental awareness, and community engagement. However, coordinators must navigate resources-related challenges, curriculum integration, sustainability, and finding the right balance to ensure the program's success and long-term impact on the school community.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The purpose of the study in the conducted phenomenological inquiry on the opportunities and challenges coordinators face in strengthening the school through a garden program delved deeply into the lived experiences, perceptions, and understanding of these coordinators. The research approach of phenomenology study sought to explore and comprehend the essence of human experiences related to a particular phenomenon. In this case, the phenomenon was the role of coordinators in enhancing the educational environment through a school garden program. Phenomenology aimed to uncover the unique experiences, thoughts, emotions, and perspectives of coordinators engaged in implementing and managing school garden programs. Doing so enabled a rich and nuanced understanding of their roles, challenges, and successes. Phenomenological inquiry helped capture the coordinators' perceptions regarding the opportunities presented by school garden programs. It seeks to elucidate how coordinators view a garden program's potential benefits, educational enhancements, and positive impacts within a school setting. Phenomenology allowed for a deep exploration of the challenges coordinators face when striving to strengthen the school through a garden program. This includes understanding their difficulties, resource limitations, and the emotional toll it might take. Through phenomenological research, coordinators' motivations, passions, and commitment can be brought to the forefront. This highlights why coordinators engage in garden programs and what drives them to overcome challenges. By exploring coordinators' experiences, phenomenology helps identify strategies and approaches that have successfully strengthened schools through garden programs. These insights can inform best practices and guide future initiatives. Ultimately, the study aims to enhance the effectiveness of school garden programs by gaining a comprehensive understanding of coordinators' experiences. The findings can inform policy, training programs, and support mechanisms, contributing to the overall success of garden initiatives. The purpose of employing phenomenological inquiry in this study is to gain an in-depth understanding of coordinators' experiences, perceptions of opportunities and challenges, motivations, and strategies in their efforts to strengthen schools through garden programs. This understanding can be instrumental in enhancing the effectiveness and impact of such programs in educational settings.

1.2. Research Questions—The study intended to gain insights and opportunities for coordinators to strengthen the school-based garden program. Specifically, the study sought answers to the following questions:

- (1) What are the coordinators' opportunities and challenges in strengthening the School-Based Garden Program?
- (2) How do coordinators cope with the challenges in strengthening the School-Based Garden Program?
- (3) What are the insights gained from the findings of this study?

1.3. Definition of Terms—The following term were operationally defined to make this study more comprehensive. School Inside A Garden Program (SIGA). This is an initiative of DepEd to support the national goal of a "Clean and Green" Society. The focus is on

growing flowers, medicinal herbs, exotic plants, and fruit-bearing trees. Through this program, learners are given an opportunity to care for

plants, flowers, and trees. This also supports one of DepEd’s core values, which is “Makakalikasan.”

1.4. Significant of the Study—The highlights of this study are significant to the following: This study helps policymakers develop policies that encourage the integration of garden programs into the curriculum and establish guidelines for their implementation. Allocate necessary financial resources to support the establishment and maintenance of school gardens. Collaborate with education experts and stakeholders to design policies that align with educational goals and sustainability objectives. Regularly assess the impact of the policies and make necessary adjustments to optimize the outcomes of the garden programs; School heads provide overall leadership and oversight for the garden program within the school. Allocate resources, including space, budget, and workforce, to support the garden program. Develop a strategic plan for integrating the garden program into the school’s educational activities, ensuring alignment with the curriculum. Organize training sessions for teachers to equip them with the knowledge and skills needed to incorporate the garden program effectively into their teaching; Teachers incorporate garden-related activities into lesson plans and align them with their teaching subjects. Supervise and guide students in the garden, facilitating learning experiences and encouraging participation. Integrate garden-based learning experiences into the teaching process to enhance students’ understanding of various subjects. Assess students’ progress, participa-

tion, and understanding of the concepts learned through the garden program; Learners are actively engaging in gardening activities and related learning experiences. They may acquire knowledge about gardening, agriculture, nutrition, and sustainability through practical experiences. Take ownership of the garden, contribute to its maintenance, and follow sustainable gardening practices. Use the garden as a living laboratory to explore and apply theoretical knowledge gained in the classroom; Research enthusiasts Research the effectiveness and impact of garden programs on education, health, and the environment. Share research findings to inform policy decisions and educational practices related to school garden programs. Design robust research methodologies that capture the diverse aspects of school garden programs and their influence on the educational community. Collaborate with schools and educational institutions to gather data and insights, ensuring a well-rounded understanding of the subject matter. Each stakeholder in a school garden program plays a crucial role in its success. Policymakers set the framework, school heads provide guidance, teachers facilitate learning, learners actively engage, and research enthusiasts contribute valuable insights. Collaborative efforts and effective coordination among these stakeholders are essential for reaping the benefits of integrating gardens into the educational setting.

1.5. Theoretical Lens—This study was anchored on strengthening a school garden program that requires effective coordination and management. Coordinators play a vital role in overseeing and organizing various aspects of the

program. Experiential Learning and Environmental Education Theory. Experiential Learning Theory by David A. Kolb. Opportunity: School garden programs provide a hands-on, experiential learning environment that aligns with

Kolb's theory. Coordinators can leverage this to enhance students' understanding of environmental concepts and foster holistic learning. Experiential Learning Theory, developed by David A. Kolb, is a widely recognized and influential model to understand learning from experience. Kolb's theory suggests that learning is a continuous cycle that involves concrete experience, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization, and active experimentation. The learning cycle consists of four stages: (a) Concrete Experience (CE) is the initial stage where learners have a specific experience or encounter a new situation. (b) Reflective Observation (RO): After the experience, learners reflect on what happened during the experience. They consider their observations and reactions, trying to understand the experience from different perspectives. (c) Abstract Conceptualization (AC): In this stage, learners try to make sense of the experience by creating generalizations, theories, or concepts. They integrate their observations and reflections into a broader understanding or framework. (d) Active Experimentation (AE): Finally, learners test their understanding and theories by applying them in new situations or future experiences. They actively experiment and apply what they have learned. The learning cycle is continuous and adaptable, allowing individuals to revisit and revise their understanding through subsequent experiences. Kolb's theory

emphasizes integrating these four stages to promote effective learning. It suggests that meaningful learning occurs when individuals engage in all four stages, creating a learning cycle that enhances their understanding and abilities. Applying this theory to education, instructors can design learning experiences encompassing all four stages, encouraging students to engage actively with the material, reflect on their experiences, derive conceptual understanding, and apply their knowledge in practical situations. This approach promotes a deeper understanding of the subject and enhances critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework of the study. This study conceptualized the experiences and coping mechanisms of coordinators in strengthening the school-based Garden Program and insights drawn from its findings. These three interconnected working themes are the focus of the study, which explores coordinators' practices regarding their opportunities and challenges while strengthening the School-Based Garden Program. The primary focus of the program is on establishing schools inside gardens, mainly featuring flowering plants and endemic and native trees such as, but not limited to, Narra Tree (*Pterocarpus indicus*) and Banaba (*Lagerstroemia speciosa*). This would make campuses throughout the country green and colorful.

2. Methodology

This chapter presents the method, research participants, data collection, role of the researcher, data analysis, trustworthiness of the study, and ethical considerations. The facts and knowledge explored in this study necessitate the consequent design and implementation, as elaborated in this chapter.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption is a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret the data collected in a specific field of study. It establishes the background used for the following con-

clusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types and are elaborated below. *Ontology*. This part of the research pertains to how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2012), real-

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

ity is subjective and multiple, as seen by the study participants. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. The reality was constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, the researcher relied on the voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes and themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The participant's answers to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct the commonality and discreteness of responses. The researcher made sure that the participants' responses were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precluded from making personal bias as the study progressed. Epistemology. This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims are justified by staying as

close to the participants as possible during the study to obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln, as cited by Creswell (2012), state that on the epistemological assumption, the researcher would attempt to lessen the distance between themselves and the participants. It is suggested that being a researcher, it was expected that time was spent in the field with participants, and becomes an 'insider.' It was assumed that the researcher established a close interaction with the participants to gain direct information that shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry. Axiology refers to the role of values in research. Creswell (2012) states that the role of values in a study is significant. Axiology suggested that the researcher openly discussed values that shaped the narrative and included their interpretation in conjunction with the participants' interpretation. The researcher upheld the dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants. The researcher understood the personal and value-laden nature of the information gathered

from the study. The researcher preserved the merit of the participants' answers and carefully understood the answers in the light of the participants' interpretation. Rhetoric meant reporting what reality was through the eyes of my research participants. The researcher used personal voice and qualitative terms such as credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability instead of internal and external validity and objectivity. Patton (2000) defined phenomenology as an inquiry that asks, "What is the structure and essence of the experience of his phenomenon for these people? This research study aimed to work well with this definition in trying to understand the coordinators' experiences in strengthening the School-Based Garden Program. Guba (2007) pointed out that the researcher needs to prepare for an in-

vestigation greater in depth and breadth than the offered description implied. He suggested the information be viewed as only "the tip of the iceberg." The researcher implemented the qualitative research method of phenomenology to allow for the exploration of the coordinators' experiences in strengthening a program. Burns and Groe (2003) stated that phenomenology is a philosophy, an approach or perspective to living, learning and doing research". Phenomenological research aims to capture lived experiences, find meaning that may or may not be known to the person who experienced them, and describe the phenomenon through the composite narrative. For the qualitative researcher, the only reality was the reality of the participants involved in the research situations constructed.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—A phenomenological approach was chosen for this study, using qualitative methodology. This study used an in-depth interview. Researcher conducted the interview using interview guide made by the researcher, which the participants answered based on their experiences and practices that were related in this study. An in-depth interview was a qualitative research technique involving intensive individual interviews with a few respondents to explore their perspectives on a particular idea, program, or situation

(Boyce Neale, 2006). Interviews are primarily done in qualitative research and occur when researchers ask one or more participants general, open-ended questions and record their answers. To gain a broader insight, a phenomenological approach is used. Phenomenology was an approach to qualitative research focusing on the commonality of a lived experience within a particular group. The fundamental goal of the approach was to describe the nature of the particular phenomenon for investigatory inquiry (Creswell, 2013).

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—The study utilized a qualitative research method employing a phenomenological qualitative design. According to Lester, phenomenological research was concerned with the study of experiences from the perspective of the individual, "bracketing" taken-for-granted assumptions, and usual ways of perceiving. The phenomenological approach is based on a paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity. It emphasized the

importance of personal perspective and interpretation. Thus, it is powerful for understanding subjective experiences, gaining insights into participants' motivations and actions, and cutting through the clutter of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom. Qualitative research mainly was associated with words, language, and experiences rather than measurements, statistics, and numerical figures. Qualitative research refers to the inductive, holistic,

epic, subjective, and process-oriented methods used to understand, interpret, describe, and develop a theory on phenomena or settings. It was a systematic, subjective approach used to describe life experiences and give them meaning (Burns Grove 2003). The phenomenological research design was selected in this study to collect data on the opportunities and challenges of coordinators in strengthening a School-Based Garden Program. This research approach deepened the understanding of nature and the meaning of everyday experiences. According to Corbetta (2003), the phenomenological research design is a qualitative type of research for which interviews provide an in-depth method that can grant access to deep knowledge and explanations and help to grasp the subject's perspective. Bryman (2012) posited that personal and detailed stories could be told through interviews or face-to-face discussions, focusing on how the interviewee understands and explains different phenomena. The researcher aimed to draw an in-depth study of the coordinator's experiences as to the opportunities and challenges experienced while strengthening the School-Based Garden Program. Qualitative research was interested in understanding how people interpret their experiences, how they construct their worlds, and what meaning they attribute to their experiences" (Merriam, 2009). This form of research would provide a deep understanding of the subject and results in enhanced explanatory power. The researcher becomes "a part of the world they study; the knower and the known are taken to be inseparable" (Hatch, 2002). Because of the researcher's involvement, however, "much qualitative research is subjective. . ." (Wrench, Thomas-Maddox, Richmond, and McCroskey, 2008) Bloomberg and Volpe, (2008) described qualitative research as "idea generation." Its design was proposed up front, but open and emergent, rather than rigid and fixed to permit exploration. It uses small samples purposefully. They occurred within natural contexts, and real-world situations were studied as they unfolded. It was a framework that allowed for flexibility and creativity. The qualitative research explored and described coordinators' opportunities and coping mechanisms with the challenges in strengthening the School Inside a Garden Program (SIGA). The research technique used was a modified Van Kaam method described by Moustakas (2000) based on recorded and transcribed interviews using semi-structured questions to capture the coordinators' experiences in strengthening the SIGA program. Specifically, phenomenology was the study of the subjective experiences of others. It researched the world through another person's eyes by discovering how they interpret their experiences. It describes the meaning of the lived experiences of several individuals about a concept or a phenomenon. Phenomenology explores the structures of consciousness in human experiences, as Polkinghorne (2000) noted. This involved procedures which the qualitative researchers should follow. First, the researcher wrote research questions that would explore the meaning of life experiences for individuals and asked individuals to describe these experiences. The researcher collected data from individuals who had experienced the phenomenon under investigation, typically via lengthy interviews. Next, the data analysis involved horizontalization, which extracted significant statements from transcribed interviews. The significant statements were transformed into clusters of meanings according to how each would fall under specific psychological and phenomenological concepts. Moreover, these transformations were tied up together to make a general description of the experience – both the textual description of what was experienced and the structural description of how it was experienced. The researcher incorporated their meaning of the experience here. Finally, the report wrote such that readers understand better the essential, invariant structure of the essence of

the experience. Conversely, several challenges have been pointed out. The researcher required a solid grounding in the philosophical guidelines of phenomenology. The subjects selected in the study were individuals who had experienced the phenomenon. The researcher needed to bracket their experiences and observations, which was difficult. The researcher needed to decide as to how and when their observations were incorporated into the study. Accordingly, Hycner, (2008) phenomenology in business research studies ideas were generated from the abundant amount of data using induction and human interests, as well as stakeholder perspective may have their reflection on the study. A study that attempted to discover the opportunities and challenges of school coordinators in strengthening the School Inside A Garden Program is a relevant example of research with a phenomenology philosophy. Advantages associated with phenomenology include a better understanding of meanings attached by people and its contribution to developing new theories. Its disadvantages include difficulties with analysis and interpretation, usually lower levels of validity and reliability compared to positivism, and more time and other resources required for data collection (Hycner, 2008). Similarly,

Schutz (2010) stressed that the purpose of the phenomenological approach is to illuminate the specific phenomena and identify them through how the actors perceive them in a situation. In the human sphere, this translates typically into gathering ‘deep’ information and perceptions through inductive, qualitative methods such as interviews, discussions, and participant observation and representing it from the perspective of the research participant(s). Phenomenology is concerned with the study of experience from the perspective of the individual, ‘bracketing’ taken-for-granted assumptions, and usual ways of perceiving. Epistemologically, phenomenological approaches were based on the paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity and emphasized the importance of personal perspective and interpretation. As such, they were dominant in understanding the subjective experience, gaining insights into people’s motivations and actions, and cutting through the clutter of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom. The researcher’s purpose was to employ the phenomenology type of qualitative method research since the focal point of this study was to uncover coordinators’ opportunities and coping mechanisms with the challenges in strengthening the SIGA program.

2.4. Research Participants—The critical informants of this study were the selected school coordinators of the School Inside A Garden Program (SIGA) of Sta. Cruz North District, Division of Davao Del Sur. The researcher utilized ten (10) teachers for qualitative participants in an in-depth interview (IDE) randomly selected from different district elementary schools. The informants should have been SIGA coordinators for at least one school year, teaching three years or more with their perma-

nent appointment regardless of sex and marital status. Data were collected through the one-on-one interview process and qualitative survey instruments. The researcher utilized the purposive sampling design since the participants were chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study. It was also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The selection of the participants will be purposefully done to ensure that the findings will be authentic (Marshall, 1996).

2.5. Ethical Considerations—

The ethical considerations were of paramount importance in the design of this research study. The researcher needed to consider several ethical issues about the research participant groups addressed in this fieldwork. Ethical considerations can be specified as one of the most critical parts of the research. The researcher must also promote the research aims by imparting factual knowledge and truth and preventing errors. Social Value. Research was essential to society. In this study, the social value focuses on the experiences of SIGA coordinators' in strengthening the SIGA program. Thus, the social problem that pushed the researcher's interest was the challenges they experienced while strengthening the program. This study could serve as a basis for the higher authorities to create more programs and resolutions from which classroom teachers could benefit. Informed Consent. Gaining the trust and support of research participants is critical to informed and ethical academic inquiry and phenomenological research (Walker, 2007, as cited by Pellerin, 2012). All participants were given an informed consent form before scheduling the interviews and participating in the phenomenological research process. Each participant was required to provide a signed personal acknowledgment, consent, and an indication of a willingness to participate in the study release. The purpose of the informed consent letter was to introduce the research effort, provide contact information, articulate the study's intent, request voluntary participation by the recipients, and identify the anticipated information that the informants are expected to provide. All participants were then required to sign and return the consent letter to the researcher before participating. In the conduct and practice of this study, the Treaty Principle of Participation, as cited by McLeod (2009), was adhered to. The invitation to participate ensured that participation in the research was entirely voluntary and based on understanding adequate information. The participants' recruitment and selection were lodged in the appendices of this study. The Vulnerability of Research Participants. The participants of this study were deemed capable of answering the research instrument, for they were all professional teachers in public elementary schools. Thus, the researcher then assured the participants that they could easily be reached through their contact number and address if there were some clarifications or questions about the study. Risks, Benefits, and Safety. The recruitment of the respondents was free of coercion, undue influence, or inducement. Moreover, respondents were provided with the contact numbers of the panel chair or panel members in case they had queries related to the study. This was done to answer the respondents' possible questions. Furthermore, if respondents experienced possible discomfort and inconvenience while answering the questions, they were not compelled to participate in any manner. Further, the researcher had to ensure the respondents were safe during the survey and interview. Thus, the questionnaire was distributed in a safe venue and administered at a convenient time. The dominant concern of this study was the Treaty Principle of Protection, as reflected in the respect for the rights of privacy and confidentiality, as well as risk minimization. This was done by assigning pseudonyms for each informant so as not to disclose their identity. The possibility of a degree of risk inherent to this was minimized by taking all reasonable steps to guarantee participant confidentiality. Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2002 to ensure that the data cannot be traced back to their authentic sources to protect participants' identities. Thus, utmost care was taken to ensure the anonymity of the data sources. Hence, any printed outputs that were carried out from this study were kept anonymous. Furthermore, all the issues were considered so there would be

no conflict of interest among the researcher and the respondents. Any misleading information and representation of primary data findings in a biased way must be avoided. Justice. The respondents were informed of the researcher's role and their corresponding role during data gathering. They were then briefed that they had to give their complete honesty in answering the survey questions, and additionally, any communication about the research should be done with honesty. Similarly, they were informed that they would benefit first from the study results. Transparency. The results of the study can then be accessed by the respondents and heads of the participating schools because the information is available and is placed on CD or other storage devices, which can be requested from the researcher. Also, by learning about the study's results, classroom teachers would be aware of the significance of the study and its contribution to their well-being. Further, each participant was advised that he/she had the right to withdraw their information at any time up to the completion of the data collection process and that they could request to be allowed to verify their transcript after the interview was carried out. The participants could amend or remove any information they felt might identify them. The researcher reserved the right to employ pseudonyms and change names and non-significant dates to protect the participant's identity in all subsequent data analysis and reporting. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher ensured the possession of the needed qualifications to conduct the study. The researcher had completed the academic requirements and passed the comprehensive examination before

thesis writing, the last requirement to obtain the researcher's master's degree. They were qualified to conduct the study physically, mentally, emotionally, and financially. Also, the advisee-adviser tandem ensures that the study was completed. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher strived to complete the study successfully within the specified time, and they were equipped with the necessary resources. Likewise, the technical committee would help enhance the paper by giving suggestions and recommendations. The researcher also had to ensure that she/he had enough funds to continue and finish the research. Community Involvement. The researcher respected the respondents' local traditions, culture, and views in this study. Moreover, this study did not involve any use of deceit in any stage of its implementation, specifically in the recruitment of the participants or methods of data collection. Furthermore, the researcher deemed it necessary to express their great pleasure for their whole-hearted participation in this study. Plagiarism and Fabrication as the researcher. The researcher respected other works by adequately citing the author and rewriting what someone else has said in their way. Understand the study context and avoid copying and pasting the text verbatim from the reference paper. Always use quotes to indicate that the text has been taken from another paper. Similarly, they would assure them of honesty in working on the manuscript and that there was no intentional misrepresentation in the study and making up of data and results or purposefully putting forward conclusions that are not accurate.

2.6. *Role of the Researcher*—The researcher wrote a letter asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. After this, another permission letter was secured and submitted to the participants. Upon approval, I used

the forms of data collection prescribed in the qualitative design. In this study, an in-depth interview was recorded. The researcher needs to get the subjective interaction between the study participants. The researcher relied heavily on

naturalistic methods (interviewing and audio-recording), using the interpretivist paradigm. Interpretive approaches rely heavily on naturalistic methods like interviewing, observation, and analysis of existing texts. These methods ensure an adequate dialog between the researchers and those with whom they interact to construct a meaningful reality collaboratively. As cited by Aquilam (2014), Yin suggested numerous forms of data collection, including documents, archival records, interviews, direct observation, participant observation, and physical artifacts. The researcher conducted an in-depth interview and focus group discussion to obtain legitimate

and trustworthy data on teachers' experiences. This interview aimed to explore the experiences of school coordinators regarding the opportunities and coping mechanisms for the challenges of strengthening the School Inside A Garden (SIGA) Program. The participants were encouraged to express their answers most comfortably. The interview with the teachers was transcribed word for word. Lastly, the researcher analyzed the data collected using discourse analysis and thematic analysis. Creswell (2007) suggested that to succeed in the study, the data must be stored to be easily found and protected from damage and loss.

2.7. Data Collection—To ensure safe educational continuity and acknowledge the challenge of COVID-19, this study adhered to the Department of Health (DOH) Administrative Order No. 2020-0015, or the Guidelines on the Risk-Based Public Health Standards for COVID-19 Mitigation, cited by the IATF to aid all sectors in all settings in implementing non-pharmaceutical interventions. The following was the step-by-step process of gathering the data needed. Asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. The researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study in the identified school. The researcher sent a letter addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent with Chapters 1 and 2 attached, together with the research instrument, which explains the study's objectives and the identification of the participants. The researcher waited for the response of the SDS before conducting the study. Asking permission from the school heads. After securing the approval of the SDS, the researcher sent letters to the principals of the schools explaining the study to be conducted in their schools. Obtaining consent from the participants. The researcher asked permission from the participants. They were for-

mally oriented about the study and the process they would undergo as participants. Conducting the interview. The researcher conducted the in-depth interview using the interview questionnaire. The profile of the participants was taken, notes were jotted down, and conversations were recorded using a sound recorder for ease of transcription. The researcher carefully listened and responded actively during the interviews. Transcribing the responses of the interviewees. The researcher precisely transcribed the interviewees' responses by recalling their answers from the sound recorder. Since the participants used their vernacular language, the researcher translated it into English language. Data Coding and thematizing. After the transcription, the data were then categorized and coded. Then, themes were extracted, and individual data within the participants were compared and contrasted. The researcher then conducts a second round of interviews (FGD) to corroborate any data that needs further explanation and input from the participants; additional information gathered was examined thoroughly and integrated into the existing body of data. After this, data were compared and contrasted between the participants to develop patterns and trends.

2.8. *Data Analysis*—In this study, thematic analysis was utilized to analyze the gathered data. The researcher analyzed the answers of the participants from the interviews conducted using Creswell’s Model, specifically the identifying of themes approach. According to Creswell (2012), themes in qualitative research are similar codes aggregated together to form a significant idea in the database. Familiarization with the data is common to all forms of qualitative analysis; the researcher immersed herself in and became intimately familiar with the data, reading and re-reading the data and noting any initial analytic observations. Coding was also a common element of many approaches to qualitative analysis and involves generating pithy labels for essential features of the data of relevance to the (broad) research question guiding the analysis. Coding is not simply a data reduction method; it is also an analytic process, so

codes capture both a semantic and conceptual reading of the data. The researcher will code every data item and end this phase by collating all their codes and relevant data extracts. Searching for themes was a coherent and meaningful pattern in the data relevant to the research question. The researcher would end this phase by collating all the coded data relevant to each theme. Reviewing themes. The researcher reflected on whether the themes tell a convincing and compelling story about the data and began to define the nature of each theme and the relationship between the themes. Defining and naming themes: The researcher prepared a detailed analysis of each theme, identifying the ‘essence’ of each theme and constructing a concise, punchy, and informative name for each theme. Writing up involves weaving together the analytic narrative and data extracts to tell the reader a coherent and persuasive story about the data and contextualizing it about existing literature.

2.9. *Framework of Analysis*—The framework analysis of this research was flexible to allow the researcher to either collect all the data and then analyze it or do data analysis during the collection process. The data was sifted, charted, and sorted by key issues and themes in the analysis stage. This involves a five-step process: (1) familiarization, (2) identifying a thematic framework, (3) indexing, (4) charting, and (5) mapping and interpretation (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Familiarization refers to the process during which the researcher was familiarized with the transcripts of the data collected: interview or focus group transcripts, observation, or field notes. Moreover, gain an overview of the collected data (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). In other words, the researcher becomes immersed in the data by listening to audiotapes, studying the field, or reading the transcripts. Throughout this process, the researcher becomes aware of critical ideas and recurrent themes and notes them.

Due to the sheer volume of data that can be collected in qualitative research, the researcher may be unable to review all the material. Thus, a selection of the data set was utilized. The selection would depend on several aspects of the data collection process. For example, the mix of methods used (e.g., interviews, documents, observations), The second stage of identifying a thematic framework occurs after familiarization when the researcher recognizes emerging themes or issues in the data set. These emerging themes or issues may have arisen from a priori themes; however, at this stage, the researcher must allow the data to dictate the themes and issues. The researcher used the notes taken during the familiarization stage to achieve this end. The key issues, concepts, and themes that the participants expressed formed the basis of a thematic framework used to filter and classify the data (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Indexing means identifying data portions or sections correspond-

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

ing to a particular theme. This process was applied to all the textual data that had been gathered from transcripts of interviews. For convenience, Ritchie and Spencer recommend that a numerical system be used to index references and annotate them in the margin beside the text (1994). Qualitative data analysis tools are ideal for such a task. The final stage, mapping, and interpretation, involved the analysis of the key characteristics as laid out in the charts. This analysis should be able to provide a schematic diagram of the event/phenomenon, thus guiding

the researcher in their interpretation of the data set. At this point, the researcher is cognizant of the objectives of qualitative analysis: “defining concepts, mapping range and nature of phenomena, creating typologies, finding associations, providing explanations, and developing strategies” (Ritchie Spencer, 1994, p. 186). Once again, these concepts, technologies, and associations were reflective of the participant. Therefore, any strategy or recommendations made by the researcher echo the actual attitudes, beliefs, and values of the participants.

2.10. *Trustworthiness of the Study—*

The concepts of validity and reliability would be relatively foreign to the field of qualitative research. Qualitative researchers substitute data trustworthiness instead of focusing on reliability and validity. Trustworthiness consists of the components such as credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability (Harts, 2016). Credibility refers to the extent to which a research account is believable and appropriate, with particular reference to the level of agreement between participants and the researcher. The notion of credibility is most often associated with the framework presented by Yvonna Lincoln and Egon Guba. Transferability the degree to which the results of qualitative research can be transferred to other contexts or settings with other respondents. The researcher facilitates the transferability judgment by a potential user through thick description. Dependability is the extent to which the study could be repeated by other researchers and that the findings would be consistent. In other words, if a person wanted to replicate your study, they should have enough information from your research report to do so and obtain similar findings as your study did. Conformability refers to the objectivity of research during data collection and data analysis. There needs to be congruency between two or more independent persons about the accuracy, relevance, or meaning of the data (Polit Beck, 2012). Conformability also indicates a means to demonstrate quality.

3. Results and Discussion

In this chapter, the study's results are presented, and the aim of the study is discussed. The themes that emerged from the data gathered were discussed in this chapter. The results present the description and background of the participants assigned to pseudonyms to conceal their identity.

3.1. Opportunities and Challenges of Coordinators in Strengthening School-Based Garden Program—This research delved into a critical facet of the educational landscape. School-based Garden programs have emerged as powerful tools for promoting experiential learning, fostering environmental stewardship, and encouraging healthy lifestyles among students. These programs offer a unique opportunity to integrate hands-on learning into the curriculum while instilling a sense of responsibility and connection to the natural world. At the heart of every successful school garden program is a dedicated coordinator who drives its development and sustainability. In this research, the significant role of coordinators in strengthening school-based garden programs was explored by identifying and capitalizing on various opportunities. From curriculum integration to community partnerships, coordinators play a pivotal role in creating engaging and impactful student garden experiences. By leveraging these opportunities effectively, coordinators can contribute to the holistic development of students while nurturing a culture of environmental awareness and healthy living within the school community.

3.1.1. Environmental Education—The participants described that in recent years, there has been a growing recognition of the importance of environmental education in schools as a means to cultivate ecological literacy and inspire sustainable practices among students. School-based garden programs offer a unique platform for integrating environmental education into the curriculum, providing hands-on experiences that deepen students' understanding of ecological principles and foster a sense of stewardship towards the environment. At the forefront of these initiatives are coordinators who play a pivotal role in identifying and capi-

talizing on opportunities to strengthen environmental education within school-based garden programs. In this research, we delved into the significant opportunities that coordinators have in enhancing environmental education through school-based garden programs. By leveraging these opportunities effectively, coordinators can empower students to become environmentally conscious individuals who are equipped to address pressing environmental challenges and contribute to building a more sustainable future. The participants also stated that this school-based garden programs have emerged as dynamic educational platforms that not only foster a deeper connection to nature but also provide invaluable opportunities for environmental education. At the helm of these initiatives are coordinators who play a pivotal role in maximizing the impact of such programs. In this research, we explore the significant opportunities coordinators have in strengthening environmental education within school-based garden programs. From instilling a sense of environmental stewardship to facilitating hands-on learning experiences, coordinators are instrumental in creating engaging educational envi-

3.1.2. Community Partnership—One of the participants voiced that school-based garden programs offer a rich tapestry of opportunities for students to engage with nature, learn about food systems, and cultivate valuable life skills. At the heart of these programs are dedicated coordinators who serve as catalysts for growth and innovation. One crucial avenue through which coordinators can enhance the impact of school-based garden programs is through community partnerships. In this research, we explore the significant opportunities that coordinators have to strengthen school-based garden programs through community partnerships. By leveraging these collaborations effectively, coordinators can broaden the scope of the program, access additional resources, and provide students with

environments where students can explore ecological concepts firsthand. By leveraging these opportunities effectively, coordinators empower students to become environmentally conscious individuals who are equipped with the knowledge and skills needed to address environmental challenges in their communities and beyond. A meta-analysis by Sobel (2004) stated that school gardens provide opportunities for experiential learning in nature, allowing students to engage directly with plants, soil, and ecosystems. Coordinators can leverage garden-based activities to facilitate hands-on learning experiences that deepen students' understanding of environmental concepts and foster a sense of stewardship for the natural world. According to a study by Lieberman Hoody (2008), experiential learning in nature has been shown to enhance students' academic achievement, environmental literacy, and personal development. Coordinators can design garden-based lessons that integrate multiple subject areas, such as science, math, language arts, and social studies, to provide interdisciplinary learning experiences that are meaningful and relevant to students.

enriching experiences that extend beyond the classroom. From collaborating with local businesses to engaging with non-profit organizations and universities, coordinators play a pivotal role in forging meaningful connections within the community. These partnerships can bring expertise, funding, and volunteer support, enriching the educational experience and fostering a sense of belonging and interconnectedness among students. According to the participants, community partnerships offer a wealth of benefits for school-based garden programs. They can bring in expertise in areas such as gardening, nutrition, and environmental education, as well as financial support, donations of materials, and volunteer assistance. Moreover, partnerships with local businesses and organizations can open up

opportunities for field trips, guest speakers, and real-world learning experiences that complement classroom instruction. In this overview, we will explore the various ways in which coordinators can harness the power of community partnerships to strengthen school-based garden programs, ultimately empowering students to become informed, engaged, and active participants in their local communities. Through collaborative efforts, coordinators can cultivate thriving garden programs that inspire students to connect with nature, foster healthy habits, and cultivate a sense of environmental responsibility. Research by Krasny et al. (2014) stated that engaging with community partners expands coordinators' access to diverse resources and expertise that may not be available within the

3.1.3. Life Skills Development—By actively participating, coordinators have in leveraging school-based garden programs to enhance the development of life skills among students. By fostering a supportive and inclusive learning environment, coordinators can empower students to cultivate valuable skills that are essential for success in both academic and real-world settings. From planning and planting to maintenance and harvest, school-based garden programs offer a wealth of experiential learning opportunities that foster collaboration, critical thinking, and resilience. Coordinators can facilitate hands-on activities, group projects, and leadership roles within the garden, providing students with opportunities to practice and refine their life skills in a meaningful context. As a participant in a school-based garden program, from teamwork and problem-solving to communication and leadership, coordinators play a pivotal role in creating opportunities for students to acquire and hone valuable life skills within the context of the garden program. By fostering a supportive and inclusive learning environment, coordinators empower students to take ownership of their learning and develop the

school community. Partnerships with local universities, extension programs, and environmental organizations can provide access to research-based information, professional development opportunities, and curriculum resources to support garden-based learning. A study by Guitart et al. (2012) suggested that community partnerships offer access to resources and expertise that can enhance the quality and sustainability of school-based garden programs. Coordinators collaborate with local businesses, gardening clubs, nurseries, and agricultural organizations to secure donations of seeds, plants, tools, and materials, as well as expert advice on garden design, maintenance, and educational programming.

skills necessary for success in both academic and real-world settings. Through intentional planning, hands-on experiences, and mentorship, coordinators can cultivate a generation of resilient, resourceful, and empowered individuals who are prepared to navigate the challenges and opportunities of the future. Kings (2007) underscored the importance of school-based garden programs promote the development of personal and social responsibility among students as they take ownership of garden projects and contribute to their care and maintenance. Coordinators can assign roles and responsibilities to students, such as watering plants, weeding beds, and harvesting produce, fostering a sense of accountability and pride in their contributions to the garden community. A study by Bowker and Tearle (2007) highlighted that engaging in garden-based activities cultivates students' sense of responsibility for their environment, community, and well-being. Coordinators can facilitate discussions and activities that encourage students to reflect on the impact of their actions on the garden ecosystem, fostering a sense of stewardship and ethical responsibility towards the natural world and the broader com-

Fig. 3. Emerging themes on the opportunities and challenges of coordinators in strengthening School-Based Garden Program

community. Based on the figure, through a comprehensive analysis of participant responses, three overarching themes have emerged, each highlighting the significant opportunities for coordinators to strengthen school-based garden programs. These themes, namely environmental education, life skills development, and community partnership, underscore the multifaceted nature of coordinators' roles in facilitating impactful learning experiences within garden programs. Participants consistently emphasized the critical role of coordinators in integrating envi-

ronmental education into school-based garden programs. By leveraging the garden as a living laboratory, coordinators have the opportunity to immerse students in hands-on experiences that deepen their understanding of ecological principles, biodiversity, and sustainability. Through activities such as composting, water conservation, and native plant gardening, coordinators empower students to become informed stewards of the environment, fostering a sense of environmental responsibility and ecological literacy.

3.2. Coping mechanisms with the challenges in strengthening School-Based Garden Program—Strengthening a school-based garden program is a rewarding endeavor that comes with its own set of challenges. Coordinators and stakeholders involved in these initiatives must navigate various obstacles to ensure the success and sustainability of the program. In this research, we explore coping mechanisms that coordinators can employ to address these challenges effectively. From limited resources and seasonal constraints to maintenance issues and curriculum integration, coordinators face multifaceted challenges in strengthening school-

based garden programs. However, by employing strategic coping mechanisms, coordinators can overcome these obstacles and create a vibrant and thriving garden program that enriches students' educational experience. In this overview, we will delve into several coping mechanisms that coordinators can utilize to address the challenges of strengthening school-based garden programs. By proactively addressing these challenges and implementing effective strategies, coordinators can navigate the complexities of managing a garden program and create an environment where students can thrive and learn valuable skills.

3.2.1. Positive Response—The participants believed that as we strengthen school-based garden programs, it's essential to acknowledge the challenges that may arise along the way. From limited resources to seasonal constraints and curriculum integration, coordinators face many obstacles in creating thriving garden programs. However, it's equally important to recognize the potential for positive responses and effective coping mechanisms to address these challenges. We celebrate the resilience and creativity of coordinators as they navigate the complexities of strengthening school-based garden programs. Rather than viewing challenges as insurmountable barriers, coordinators have the opportunity to respond with innovative solutions and proactive strategies that propel the program forward. Furthermore, the participants also stressed that by embracing a positive outlook and fostering a culture of collaboration and creativity, coordinators can turn challenges into opportunities for growth and transformation within school-based garden programs. In the following sections, we will explore various coping mechanisms coordinators can employ to address critical challenges and cultivate thriving garden programs that enrich students' educational experiences. Through positive responses

3.2.2. Innovative Concepts—As coordinators strive to strengthen school-based garden programs, innovative concepts offer promising solutions to cope with the challenges that may arise along the way. In this research, we explore the integration of innovative concepts as coping mechanisms to overcome obstacles and enhance the effectiveness of school-based garden programs. Traditional garden programs may encounter challenges such as limited space, seasonal constraints, and resource limitations. However, by embracing innovative concepts, coordinators can introduce novel approaches

and proactive strategies, coordinators can create an environment where students, educators, and the broader community unite to nurture a love for gardening, environmental stewardship, and experiential learning. Together, we can cultivate flourishing school-based garden programs that empower students and inspire future generations to participate actively in creating a more sustainable world. Research by Barnes et al. (2015) highlighted that professional development and training opportunities for coordinators and educators involved in school-based garden programs are crucial coping mechanisms. Workshops, seminars, and training sessions can equip personnel with the skills, knowledge, and strategies to effectively address challenges. Continuous learning and skill development contribute to the resilience and success of garden initiatives. Moreover, studies by Beck Cable (2012) emphasized that adaptability and flexibility are essential coping mechanisms for managing challenges in school-based garden programs. Coordinators should be prepared to adjust plans and strategies in response to changing circumstances, such as weather conditions, resource availability, and student needs. An adaptable approach ensures that the garden program remains responsive and resilient in the face of challenges.

that not only address these challenges but also foster creativity, engagement, and sustainability within the program. A study by Harris et al. (2016) in integrating technology into school-based garden programs can be an innovative coping mechanism. Coordinators can utilize digital platforms, such as mobile apps or online tools, for garden planning, data collection, and educational resources. Technology can enhance communication, streamline administrative tasks, and provide access to virtual learning experiences, expanding the reach and impact of the garden program. Incorporating green in-

Fig. 4. Emerging themes on coping ways with the challenges in strengthening the School-Based Garden Program

frastructure design principles into school-based garden programs is an innovative coping mechanism. Coordinators can implement sustainable landscaping practices, such as rain gardens, bioswales, and permeable surfaces, to manage stormwater runoff and improve environmental quality. Green infrastructure design enhances the resilience and functionality of the garden space while providing valuable learning opportunities for students by BenDor et al. (2015). Urban agriculture initiatives offer innovative coping mechanisms for strengthening school-based garden programs in urban settings as stated by Blair (2009). Coordinators can explore rooftop gardens, vertical farming, hydroponics, or community garden partnerships to maximize limited space and resources.

Urban agriculture initiatives provide hands-on learning experiences and promote food security, environmental sustainability, and community engagement. Based on Figure 4, the themes that emerged from participants' responses were positive responses, professional development, and innovative concepts. Through a holistic approach that embraces optimism, continuous learning, and innovation, coordinators can navigate challenges effectively and create vibrant, engaging, and sustainable garden programs that enrich students' educational experiences. For the theme of positive responses, participants' responses underscore the importance of maintaining a positive outlook and proactive mindset when faced with challenges in school-based garden programs.

3.3. *Insights Gained from the Findings of the Study*—The participants shared their educational management insights and it was narrowed

down into one to generate the themes. These themes were carefully analyzed and formulated based on informants' accounts and reflections. The subthemes are shown below:

3.3.1. *Challenges in Sustainability*—

Research strongly supports the vital role of a stable water supply, which is essential for the success of a school garden program. With access to consistent water resources, coordinators can ensure proper hydration and irrigation of plants, leading to healthier growth and increased yield. Additionally, a stable water supply enables the implementation of water conservation practices, such as drip irrigation systems or rainwater harvesting, promoting sustainable gardening practices within the program. However, maintaining a stable water supply can be challenging, especially in areas prone to water scarcity or erratic availability. Coordinators may need to explore alternative water sources, such as water storage tanks or greywater recycling systems, to ensure reliable access to water for the school garden program. Proper fencing of the school premises can provide several benefits for the school garden program. A well-fenced area helps protect the garden from unauthorized access, vandalism, or damage caused by wildlife, pests, or stray animals. It also creates a safe and secure environment for students to engage in gardening activities, reducing the risk of accidents or injuries. However, installing and maintaining proper fencing can be a significant challenge for coordinators. Factors such as budget constraints, logistical issues, and regulatory requirements may hinder the implementation of fencing measures. Ensuring

3.3.2. Opportunities for Experiential Learning—Coordinators play a vital role in creating opportunities for experiential learning within the school garden program. By engaging students in hands-on activities such as planting, cultivating, and harvesting crops, coordinators facilitate meaningful learning experiences that promote a deeper understanding of environmental concepts and foster a sense of connection to nature. School gardens offer students hands-on opportunities to engage in authen-

the garden is well-maintained and resilient to various circumstances is crucial for the success and sustainability of a school-based garden program. Develop a comprehensive maintenance schedule that outlines tasks such as watering, weeding, pruning, and pest control. Assign specific responsibilities to students, teachers, and volunteers, and regularly review and adjust the schedule as needed to accommodate changing seasons and garden needs. Install an efficient irrigation system, such as drip irrigation or soaker hoses, to ensure consistent watering without wasting water. Regularly monitor and adjust the irrigation schedule based on weather conditions and plant requirements to prevent over or under-watering. Experiential learning in school garden programs offers opportunities for experiential learning, providing students with hands-on experiences in gardening, environmental stewardship, and sustainable practices (Blair, 2009). Interdisciplinary education where coordinators can integrate garden activities into various subjects, promoting interdisciplinary education and enhancing students' understanding of complex concepts through real-world applications (Skelly Bradley, 2017). School gardens create opportunities for teaching students about healthy eating habits, food systems, and nutrition, contributing to improved dietary choices and overall well-being (Davis Carpenter, 2009).

tic, experiential learning experiences outside of the traditional classroom setting, as viewed by Klemmer et al. (2005). By actively participating in planting, tending, and harvesting crops, students develop a deeper understanding of various subjects such as science, math, and environmental studies, according to the study by Davis and Carpenter (2009). Engaging in garden-related activities fosters a sense of ownership and responsibility among students as they witness the direct impact of their efforts on

the garden's growth and development posited by Blair, (2009). This hands-on involvement contributes to increased motivation, engage-

ment, and self-efficacy in learning as revealed by Skelly Bradley, (2017).

3.3.3. Integration of Curriculum—Integration of the curriculum presents both opportunities and challenges for coordinators in strengthening the school inside a garden program. The integration of the curriculum allows coordinators to create interdisciplinary learning experiences that transcend traditional subject boundaries. By incorporating garden-related activities into various subjects such as science, math, language arts, social studies, and health education, coordinators provide students with holistic learning opportunities that reinforce academic concepts in real-world contexts. School gardens provide a unique platform for interdisciplinary learning, where various subjects such as science, math, language arts, social studies, and health education can be integrated seamlessly (Berezowitz et al., 2015). Coordinators can leverage garden-based activities to reinforce academic concepts and skills across multiple disciplines, fostering a holistic approach to learning (Graham Zidenberg-Cherr, 2005). Integrating curriculum into school garden programs offers students opportunities to apply theoretical knowledge to real-world contexts, enhancing their understanding of academic concepts through hands-on experiences (Davis Carpenter, 2009). For example, students can explore mathematical principles such as measurement and geometry while designing garden layouts or conducting scientific investigations on plant growth and ecosystems.

Based on the study's findings on the opportunities and challenges of coordinators in strengthening the school inside a garden program, several insights can be gleaned across three main themes: challenges and sustainability, opportunities for experiential learning, and curriculum integration. Coordinators face chal-

lenges related to securing adequate resources for the maintenance and sustainability of the school garden program. This includes funding for infrastructure, tools, seeds, and ongoing maintenance costs. Coordinators must navigate seasonal challenges such as extreme weather conditions, limited growing seasons, and fluctuations in temperature and precipitation, which can impact the success and sustainability of the garden program. Ensuring the ongoing maintenance and upkeep of the school garden program poses a challenge, including tasks such as watering, weeding, pest management, and soil health maintenance. The school garden program provides valuable opportunities for experiential learning, allowing students to engage in hands-on activities such as planting, harvesting, and composting. These experiences deepen students' understanding of environmental concepts and foster a sense of connection to nature. The garden serves as an outdoor classroom where students can observe ecological processes, learn about plant life cycles, and explore concepts such as biodiversity, soil health, and sustainable agriculture in a real-world context. Through participation in the school garden program, students develop a sense of environmental stewardship and responsibility, learning about the importance of conserving natural resources, reducing waste, and promoting sustainable living practices. Coordinators have the opportunity to integrate the school garden program into the curriculum across various subject areas, including science, math, language arts, social studies, and health education. This interdisciplinary approach enhances student engagement and reinforces academic concepts in real-world contexts. Garden-based learning offers experiential learning opportunities that go beyond tradi-

Fig. 5. Emerging themes on the insights gained from the findings of the study

tional classroom instruction, providing students with hands-on experiences that deepen their understanding of curriculum content. The school garden program serves as a valuable tool for environmental education, allowing coordinators to teach students about ecological principles, sustainability, and environmental stewardship through experiential learning in the garden. In summary, the findings of the study highlight the challenges and opportunities associated with strengthening the school inside a garden program, including issues related to sustainability, experiential learning opportunities, and integration of curriculum. By addressing challenges proactively and leveraging opportunities for experiential learning and curriculum integration, coordinators can create a robust and impactful educational experience for students within the school garden program.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter discusses the implications of the opportunities and challenges coordinators face in strengthening the school-based garden program. We also explore potential future research, practice, and policy directions in this area. The opportunities and challenges coordinators face in strengthening the school inside a garden program have important implications for practice, research, and policy. By addressing these implications and exploring future directions, stakeholders could work together to promote the success and sustainability of school garden programs and enhance their impact on student learning and community well-being.

4.1. Findings—In summary, the study’s findings highlight the challenges and opportunities associated with strengthening the school inside a garden program, including issues related to sustainability, experiential learning opportunities, and curriculum integration. By addressing challenges proactively and leveraging opportunities for experiential learning and curriculum integration, coordinators can create a robust and impactful educational experience for students within the school garden program.

4.2. Implications—

By addressing these implications and exploring future directions, stakeholders can work collaboratively to promote the success and sustainability of school garden programs and enhance their impact on student learning and community well-being. This reiterates the importance of continuous improvement and development in school-based garden programs. Three overarching themes have emerged regarding the opportunities of coordinators to strengthen the School-Based Garden Program, each highlighting the significant opportunities for coordinators to strengthen school-based garden programs. These themes, namely environmental education, life skills development, and community partnership, underscore the multifaceted nature of coordinators' roles. They need to possess a diverse set of skills to facilitate impactful learning experiences within garden programs. Participants consistently emphasized the critical role of coordinators in integrating environmental education into school-based garden programs. By leveraging the garden as a living laboratory, coordinators can immerse students in hands-on experiences that deepen their understanding of ecological principles, biodiversity, and sustainability. Through activities such as composting, water conservation, and native plant gardening, coordinators empower students to become informed stewards of the environment, fostering a sense of environmental responsibility and ecological literacy. Another prominent theme identified among participant responses is the pivotal role of coordinators in facilitating life skills development within school-based garden programs. Coordinators create a nurturing environment where students can cultivate essential life skills such as teamwork, problem-solving, communication, and leadership. Through collaborative garden projects, students learn to work effectively in teams, navigate challenges, communicate ideas, and take on leadership roles. These life skills are invaluable for students' personal growth and success in academic and real-world settings. Participants also highlighted the importance of community partnerships in strengthening school-based garden programs, with coordinators as key facilitators in forging and maintaining these collaborations. By engaging with local businesses, non-profit organizations, universities, and community members, coordinators expand the resources and opportunities available to the garden program. Community partnerships provide access to expertise, funding, volunteer support, and additional educational opportunities such as field trips and guest lectures. Through these partnerships, coordinators enrich students' educational experiences, foster community engagement, and promote the sustainability of the garden program. In coping mechanisms with the challenges in strengthening the School-Based Garden Program, a holistic approach that embraces optimism, continuous learning, and innovation, coordinators can navigate challenges effectively and create vibrant, /engaging, and sustainable garden programs that enrich students' educational experience. Participants' responses underscore the importance of maintaining a positive outlook and proactive mindset when faced with challenges in school-based garden programs. By fostering resilience, creativity, and optimism, coordinators and stakeholders can transform obstacles into opportunities for growth and innovation. Positive responses involve embracing challenges as learning experiences, seeking solutions collaboratively, and celebrating successes along the way. This theme highlights the power of a positive mindset in overcoming challenges and fostering a culture of continuous improvement within school-based garden programs. Another key theme from participants' responses was the importance of professional development in enhancing the capacity of coordinators and stakeholders involved in school-based garden programs. Professional development opportunities such as workshops, training sessions, and networking events provide valu-

able resources and support to coordinators, enabling them to acquire new skills, knowledge, and strategies for effectively addressing challenges. By investing in professional development, coordinators can enhance their expertise and leadership capabilities, ultimately strengthening school-based garden programs and maximizing their impact on student learning and engagement. Participants also highlighted the significance of incorporating innovative concepts and strategies into school-based garden programs to cope with challenges and foster innovation. Innovative concepts such as vertical gardening towers, aquaponics systems, and other cutting-edge approaches offer novel solutions to overcome limited space, resources, and seasonal constraints. By embracing innovative concepts, coordinators can introduce new perspectives, techniques, and opportunities for experiential learning within school-based garden programs, ultimately enhancing their effectiveness and sustainability. Given the opportunities and challenges of coordinators in strengthening the school inside a garden program, several insights can be gleaned across three main themes: challenges and sustainability, opportunities for experiential learning, and curriculum integration. Coordinators face challenges in securing adequate resources for the maintenance and sustainability of the school garden program. This includes funding for infrastructure, tools, seeds, and ongoing maintenance costs. Coordinators must navigate seasonal challenges such as extreme weather conditions, limited growing seasons, and fluctuations in temperature and precipitation, which can impact the success and sustainability of the garden program. Ensuring the ongoing maintenance and upkeep of the school garden program poses a challenge, in-

cluding tasks such as watering, weeding, pest management, and soil health maintenance. The school garden program provides valuable opportunities for experiential learning, allowing students to engage in hands-on activities such as planting, harvesting, and composting. These experiences deepen students' understanding of environmental concepts and foster a connection to nature. The garden serves as an outdoor classroom where students can observe ecological processes, learn about plant life cycles, and explore concepts such as biodiversity, soil health, and sustainable agriculture in a real-world context. Through participation in the school garden program, students develop a sense of environmental stewardship and responsibility, learning about the importance of conserving natural resources, reducing waste, and promoting sustainable living practices. The school garden program plays a crucial role in promoting these sustainable living practices, inspiring hope for a better future. Coordinators have the opportunity to integrate the school garden program into the curriculum across various subject areas, including science, math, language arts, social studies, and health education. This interdisciplinary approach enhances student engagement and reinforces academic concepts in real-world contexts. Garden-based learning offers experiential learning opportunities beyond traditional classroom instruction, providing students with hands-on experiences that deepen their understanding of curriculum content. The school garden program serves as a valuable tool for environmental education, allowing coordinators to teach students about ecological principles, sustainability, and environmental stewardship through experiential learning in the garden.

4.3. Future Directions—Policymakers may prioritize integrating school garden programs into educational policies and frameworks

to promote their adoption and sustainability. This could include incorporating garden-based learning into curriculum standards and pro-

viding funding and resources for program implementation. Policymakers may allocate dedicated funding and resources to support establishing and maintaining school garden programs. This could include funding for infrastructure, supplies, teacher training, and ongoing maintenance costs. Policymakers may consider recognizing and incentivizing schools and coordinators that excel in implementing successful garden programs. This could include awards, grants, or other forms of recognition to encourage excellence in garden-based education and community engagement. School administrators may prioritize allocating resources and support to establish and maintain school garden programs. This includes funding infrastructure, supplies, and professional development for coordinators and teachers involved in the program. Administrators should actively seek partnerships with the local community, including parents, community organizations, and businesses, to support and sustain the school garden program. This could involve organizing community workdays, educational events, and collaborative projects. Administrators may integrate the school garden program into the broader school culture and curriculum. This includes promoting interdisciplinary learning opportunities, incorporating garden-based activities into classroom instruction, and highlighting

the program's impact on student learning and community engagement. Teachers may actively seek professional development opportunities to enhance their knowledge and skills in integrating garden-based learning into the curriculum. This includes attending workshops, training sessions, and networking events focused on garden-based education and sustainable gardening practices. Teachers may integrate garden-based activities into their lesson plans across various subjects, including science, math, language arts, social studies, and health education. This involves aligning garden activities with academic standards and learning objectives to reinforce classroom concepts and engage students in experiential learning. Teachers may actively engage students in hands-on activities and experiential learning opportunities within the school garden program. This includes involving students in planting, harvesting, and maintenance tasks and facilitating reflective discussions and inquiry-based learning experiences related to garden-based activities. By addressing these future directions, policymakers, school administrators, and teachers can work collaboratively to promote the success and sustainability of school garden programs and enhance their impact on student learning and community.

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